

PHOTOBROMINATION OF CAMPHOR AND THE INFLUENCE OF DIFFERENT SOLVENTS ON THE REACTION

By P. C. GOSWAMI

The photobromination of camphor has been carried out in CCl_4 , C_6H_6 , CS_2 and CHCl_3 in light. In all the media the reaction is strictly unimolecular. In dark, at temperatures not exceeding 80° , the reaction does not take place at all. There is no period of induction or photochemical after-effect. The velocity constants and the temperature coefficients vary widely in different solvents. No direct relationship can be found between the velocity constants and the dielectric constants of the solvents and between the temperature coefficients and the dielectric constants.

The increase of velocity constant with decrease in the concentration of Br_2 molecules is peculiar as it apparently violates Maxwell's law.

Camphor is found to take up bromine in presence of light. In dark, at temperatures not exceeding 30° , the reaction does not take place at all. Camphor is also soluble in many organic solvents. The effect of different solvents on the reaction and its kinetics are hence suitable fields for investigation.

The influence of solvents on photochemical reaction has been investigated by various workers. Winther (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1926, 120, 234) concluded that the velocity of photochemical reactions decreased as the dielectric constants of the solvents increased. In thermal reactions, however, reverse behaviour was observed. Many workers showed that no direct relationship could be obtained between the velocity coefficients and the dielectric constants of the solvents (Dhar, "Chemical Action of Light", p. 364; Mathur, Gupta and Bhatnagar, *Indian J. Phys.*, 1928, 2, 243; Yajnik and Uppal, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6, 729; Lauer *et al.*, *Ber.*, 1936, 69B, 137, 141, 851, 978, 1061; 1937, 70B, 326, 1288, 1707).

The presence of double linkages in the solvents has an accelerating action on the rate of reaction. Thus the photochemical reaction of anthracene $\rightleftharpoons$ dianthracene and also photobromination of anthracene are greater in benzene than in other media. The photoreaction is also found to be parallel to the absorption spectra in the solvent. All these show that the dielectric constant of the solvents is not the single rate-determining factor.

Although several papers have been published, yet the photoreactions in different solvents are still not numerous. Photobromination of camphor has therefore been carried out in CCl_4 , C_6H_6 , CS_2 and CHCl_3 . Diethyl ether was also tried; but it was found to be an unsuitable solvent, as the medium itself had undergone bromination at a rate even higher than the rate of bromination of camphor.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Pure, resublimed synthetic camphor and Merck's pure bromine were taken. The solvents C_6H_6 , CCl_4 , $CHCl_3$ and CS_2 were samples from Merck, Baird and Tatlock, London, Boots Pure Drug Co., Nottingham and from Bengal Chemical and Pharmaceutical Works respectively. They were further distilled before use. The reaction was carried out in a stoppered glass cell. The reactants were mixed in dark and 2 c.c. of the mixture withdrawn immediately for initial reading. The cell was then exposed to the light of a Point-o-lite lamp of 150 c.p. made parallel by a lens. Heat rays were cut off by $N/20$ - $CuSO_4$ solution. The reaction cell was kept in a double-walled thermostat having a window to allow light in. By keeping the reaction cell from the source of light at a distance of 42.5 cm. the intensity was kept constant. At various intervals of time, noted by a stop-watch, 2 c.c. of the mixture were withdrawn and after adding KI to the mixture, were titrated with approximately $N/100$ -thiosulphate solution from a microburette. The velocity constant k was calculated from the equation,

$$k = \frac{1}{t} \log_{10} \frac{a}{a-x}$$

The reaction obeys the unimolecular equation as will be seen from the following tables. The concentration given always denotes the final concentration after the reactants are mixed.

TABLE I

Solvent = benzene. Br₂ conc. = $N/37.24$. Camphor conc. = $M/20$. Temp. = 30° .

Time (min.) ..	0	30	60	90	120	150
Thio (c.c.) ...	5.88	4.96	4.56	4.24	4.01	4.00
k ...		0.00118	0.00119	0.00115	0.00107	Mean. 0.00115

Light cut off

TABLE II

Solvent = CCl_4 . Other conditions same as in Table I.

Time (min.) ...	0	45	80	115	150	180
Thio (c.c.) ...	5.12	4.68	4.36	4.08	3.80	3.60
k ...		0.000888	0.000870	0.000858	0.00863	Mean. 0.000864

Light cut off

TABLE III

Solvent = CS_2 . Other conditions same as in Table I.

Time (min.) ...	0	60	126	196	259	300
Thio (c.c.) ...	5.74	5.94	5.58	5.42	5.31	5.23
k ...		0.000128	0.000125	0.000122	0.0001222	Mean. 0.000124

Light cut off

TABLE IV

Time (min.) ...	Solvent = CHCl ₃ . Other conditions same as in Table I.						
	0	45	90	135	180	195	
Thio (c.c.) ...	4.71	4.47	4.25	4.04	3.80	3.91	
<i>k</i> ...		0.000804	0.000495	0.000493	0.000496	Light out off	Mean, 0.000497

TABLE V

Velocity constants in different media at 20° & 30°.

Medium.	<i>k</i> (20°).	<i>k</i> (30°).	Temp. coeff.
C ₆ H ₆	0.00068	0.00115	$\frac{0.00115}{0.00068} = 1.338$
CCl ₄	0.000385	0.000861	$\frac{0.000861}{0.000385} = 2.245$
CS ₂	0.000071	0.000124	$\frac{0.000124}{0.000071} = 1.746$
CHCl ₃	0.000337	0.000497	$\frac{0.000497}{0.000337} = 1.475$

TABLE VI

Relation of the dielectric const. of the solvents with velocity const. and with temp. coeff.

Medium.	Dielec. const.	<i>k</i> ^{30°} .	Temp. coeff.
CCl ₄	2.25	0.000864	2.245
C ₆ H ₆	2.29	0.00115	1.338
CS ₂	2.61	0.000124	1.746
CHCl ₃	5.14	0.000497	1.475

TABLE VII

Reaction rate with diff. conc. of Br₂.
Conc. of camphor = *M*/20

Medium.	Conc. of Br ₂	<i>k</i> ^{20°} .	Medium.	Conc. of Br ₂	<i>k</i> ^{30°} .
CCl ₄	<i>N</i> /37.24	0.000885	CS ₂	<i>N</i> /37.24	0.000071
	<i>N</i> /74.48	0.000440		<i>N</i> /74.48	0.000095
C ₆ H ₆	<i>N</i> /37.24	0.00068	CHCl ₃	<i>N</i> /37.24	0.000497
	<i>N</i> /74.48	0.00142		<i>N</i> /74.48	0.000729

} at 30°

TABLE VIII

Reaction rate with diff. conc. of camphor.
Conc. of Br₂ = *N*/37.24.

Medium.	Conc. of camphor.	<i>k</i> ^{20°} .	Medium	Conc. of camphor.	<i>k</i> ^{30°} .
CCl ₄	<i>M</i> /20	0.000964	CS ₂	<i>M</i> /40	0.00083
	<i>M</i> /40	0.00686		CHCl ₃	<i>M</i> /20
CS ₂	<i>M</i> /20	0.00124	CHCl ₃	<i>M</i> /40	0.000377

TABLE IX

*% Increase of *k* in diff. media with increase of conc. of acceptor molecules and with decrease of conc. of active molecules.*

Medium.	Dielec. const.	% Increase of <i>k</i> ^{30°} when conc. of Br ₂ is halved.	% Increase of <i>k</i> ^{30°} when conc. of camphor is doubled.
CCl ₄	2.25	14.29	25.95
C ₆ H ₆	2.29	65.1	Not tried.
CS ₂	2.61	33.8	49.4
CHCl ₃	5.14	46.68 (30°)	31.84

DISCUSSION

From Tables I to IV, the reaction is found to follow the unimolecular equation for a particular concentration of camphor and a particular concentration of Br_2 in all the media. The results also indicate that there is no period of induction or photochemical after-effect. The reaction stops as soon as the light is cut off. Table VI shows that like many other reactions, the velocity constants of this reaction hold no direct relationship with the dielectric constants of the solvents. The temperature coefficients of the reactions also bear no direct relationship with the dielectric constants of the media.

Table VII shows the interesting peculiarity that the velocity constant increases as the concentration of Br_2 is diminished. This peculiarity was also observed in a previous paper by the author (Mukherjee and Goswami, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1944, 21, 237). Ghosh and Basu (*ibid.*, 1928, 5, 343, 361) also observed this interesting peculiarity which apparently violated Maxwell's law, $n'/n = \text{constant}$ at constant temperature, where n' —number of active molecules and n —total number of molecules. In order to explain this peculiarity Ghosh and Basu (*loc. cit.*) put forward an explanation that the presence of different amounts of oxygen in the reaction system was the cause of this abnormal change in the velocity constant. Oxygen acted like an inhibitor and in concentrated solution of Br_2 , according to Ghosh and Basu, greater amount of O_2 was present which explained the smaller velocity constant in more concentrated Br_2 solution. According to them, O_2 came from two sources :

- (i). Oxygen remaining dissolved in water used in experiments.
- (ii). Oxygen obtained from the dark reaction, $\text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{Br}_2 \rightarrow 2\text{HBr} + \text{O}$.

In view of the fact, that such increase in velocity constants is also observed in non-aqueous solvents, as shown in Table VII, the applicability of similar explanation on the Oxygen theory in the present case is doubtful. The second source of oxygen is absent in non-aqueous solvents. Therefore it is doubtful that this increase is due to smaller amount of O_2 in dilute solution of Br_2 . The percentage of acceleration in the rate is greater in benzene than in others. The temperature coefficient in benzene is, however, smaller.

Table VIII shows that with the increase in the concentration of camphor molecules, the rate of the reaction increases as expected. The percentage of increase in the velocity constants with increase in the concentration of the camphor molecules or decrease in the concentration of Br_2 molecules is not uniform in all media as shown in Table IX. The nature of solvents, hence, plays some part here too.

The author expresses his sincere thanks to Prof. J. L. Mukherjee, for his kind advice, encouragement and help. The author also thanks Prof. I. B. Sarkar for the facilities offered in the laboratory to carry out this piece of work.